

Chemistry of Heterocycles. Part-IX[†]. Synthesis of Isoxazolylpyrazolones

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Isoxazolylpyrazolones (4) have been obtained by the heterocyclisation of ethyl-2-[1-phenyl-2-(3-methyl-4-nitro-5-isoxazolyl)ethyl]acetoacetates (3) with hydrazine hydrate. The latter have been produced by the Michaelation of 3-methyl-4-nitro-5-styryl-isoxazoles (2) with ethylacetoacetate in triethylamine. Interaction of the Michael adducts with phenylhydrazine gave only phenylhydrazones (6) instead of the *N*-phenylpyrazolones (5).

THOUGH ethylene diheterocycles having nitrogen are known¹, oxygen-nitrogen heterocycles of this type have not been investigated. Synthesis of ethylene diisoxazoles has been recently reported from these laboratories². In continuation of our efforts in this direction we describe the syntheses of isoxazolylpyrazolones in this paper in view of a variety of physiological activities exhibited by isoxazoles³ and pyrazolones⁴.

Regiospecific styrylation of 3,5-dimethyl-4-nitroisoxazole (1) with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of base has led to 3-methyl-4-nitro-5-styrylisoxazole, (2). Interaction of 3-methyl-4-nitro-5-styrylisoxazoles⁵ (2) with ethylacetoacetate in refluxing triethylamine for 3-4 h gave the Michael products, viz. ethyl-2-[1-phenyl-2-(3-methyl-4-nitro-5-isoxazolyl)ethyl] acetoacetates (3; M⁺, *m/z* 360). The products which have been obtained in 60-70% yields gave intense colouration with iron(III) chloride and dissolve in dilute aqueous sodium hydroxide indicating the retention of the enolizable β-dicarbonyl system.

The ir spectrum (nujol) of 3 displayed bands due to hydroxyl (3500-3400), ketonic carbonyl (1710) and ester carbonyl (1740 cm⁻¹). The ¹H nmr spectrum indicated the Michael product to be a tautomeric mixture of keto and enol forms (broad signal in the down field, exchangeable with D₂O). In the present investigation no effort has been made to estimate the relative amounts of the two tautomers. The mass spectrum of the Michael product shows the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 360.

1 R = -OH,
2 R = -CH=CH-Ar

3

4 R = H
5 R = Ph

6

The Michael adducts (3) have been refluxed with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol for 3 h. After making sure that β-ketoester being completely consumed (by ferric reaction with the aliquots of the reaction mixture) the solid product was isolated by pouring the contents into cold water followed by neutralisation with dilute hydrochloric acid. On the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data, the product of the reaction has been identified as 4-[α-(3-methyl-4-nitro-5-isoxazolyl) methyl]benzyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (4). A broad band in the region 3400-3100 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectrum indicated the presence of N-H in the molecule. Varying the aromatic aldehydes, ten ethylene diheterocycles have been obtained.

Equimolar amounts of the Michael products and phenylhydrazine in ethanol containing few drops of acetic acid were stirred at ambient temperatures. The solid products were separated in 10 min and were found to be the hydrazones (6) of the β-keto esters rather than the expected *N*-phenylpyrazolones (5) on the basis of ir (3350 cm⁻¹) and nmr spectral data (δ 8.3, exchanged with 1FA, NH). The hydrazones did not cyclise when the reaction mixture from which they separated was put under reflux. Attempts have been made to convert the hydrazones into the pyrazolones (5). A scanning of the methods reported in literature to effect this heterocyclisation include the heating of the hydrazone as such or in an inert solvent⁶ or with acidic reagents⁷. In the present investigation, the intermediate hydrazones have been subjected to pyrolysis

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in decalin, diphenyl ether and xylene. Under these conditions, the reaction gave back either the starting materials (xylene) or dark coloured substances which could neither be characterised nor purified. Attempted cyclisation with acetic anhydride in the presence or absence of traces of concentrated sulphuric acid again gave the starting compound. Failure to cyclise the hydrazone of a β -ketoester in the present investigation could not be explained.

The ^1H nmr spectra of the heterocyclised products supported the assigned structures (4 and 6). The broad signal centered at 13 is due to NH (disappears when the spectrum is run in TFA). The pyrazolone-CH resonates as a broad signal around 5.0. The two diastereotopic protons resonate as a singlet with a fine structure at 3.15. The multiplet centered at 4.2 is assignable to the lone tertiary proton. The two methyls show up as singlets at 1.7 and 2.3, respectively. That the product 6 is not cyclised is indicated by the signal due to N-H at 8.3 (exchanged with TFA). The tertiary proton flanked by the carbonyl and the azomethine functionalities resonate at 4.7. The ethyl group in the molecule is indicated by a three proton triplet at 0.9 and a two proton quartet at 3.95.

The mass spectrum of 4 is dominated by the fragments containing the pyrazole moiety intact and the isoxazole ring cleaved, thus indicating that the former is more stable than the latter to electron impact. This is in keeping with the fact that only the isoxazole ring of isoxazolyipyrazoles is cleaved on oxidation⁶.

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded in nujol mull on a Perkin-

Elmer 283 spectrophotometer. ^1H nmr spectra were run on a 90 MHz Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument at 70 eV.

General procedures :

Ethyl-2-[1-phenyl-2-(3-methyl-4-nitro-5-isoxazolyl)-ethyl]acetoacetates (3) : 3-Methyl-4-nitro-5-styrylisoxazole (2 ; 2.3 g, 10 mmol) and ethylacetoacetate (3.9 g, 30 mmol) were refluxed in triethylamine (25 ml) for 3-4 h. The reaction mixture was poured into a china dish and triethylamine evaporated at ambient temperatures. The resulting gummy product was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) several times and finally decomposed in methanol containing a few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid. The Michael product was filtered and recrystallised from methanol (Table 1).

Isoxazolyipyrazolones (4) : The β -ketoester (3 ; 1.8 g, 5 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (2 ml, 80%) were refluxed in ethanol (30 ml) for 2.5-3 h. The aliquot of the reaction mixture was tested for the complete consumption of the Michael product (colour with iron(III) chloride). The pyrazolones (5) were isolated by pouring the contents into ice-cold water followed by neutralisation with dilute hydrochloric acid and recrystallisation from suitable solvents (Table 2).

Reaction of Michael products with phenylhydrazine : The Michael products (3 ; 1.8 g mmol) and phenylhydrazine (1.0 g, 6 mmol) were stirred in ethanol (20 ml) containing few drops of acetic acid at ambient temperature. The hydrazones separated out in about 10 min, was filtered and recrystallised from suitable solvents (Table 3).

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF MICHAEL PRODUCTS (3)

Compd.	Ar	M.p.* °C	Reaction time, h	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
3a	Phenyl	148	3.0	70	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	7.95 (7.77)
3b	2-Chlorophenyl	164	3.0	65	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Cl}$	7.00 (7.10)
3c	4-Chlorophenyl	150	3.5	68	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Cl}$	6.78 (7.10)
3d	2-Bromophenyl	137	4.0	60	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Br}$	6.15 (6.37)
3e	4-Methoxyphenyl	145	3.0	70	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$	6.87 (7.17)
3f	4-Methylphenyl	137	3.0	70	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	7.07 (7.48)
3g	4-Hydroxyphenyl	156	3.5	65	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$	7.98 (7.44)
3h	3-Hydroxyphenyl	165	3.5	65	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$	7.18 (7.44)
3i	3-Nitrophenyl	182	4.0	60	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8$	10.19 (10.97)
3j	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	160	4.0	60	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_2$	6.47 (6.52)
3k	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	175	4.0	60	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_2$	6.47 (6.52)

* Recrystallisation solvent : ethanol.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF PYRAZOLONES (4)

Compd.	Ar	M.p.* °C	Reaction time, h	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
4a	Phenyl	174	3.0	40	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄	16.63 (17.00)
4b	2-Chlorophenyl	181	3.0	35	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	15.14 (15.46)
4c	2-Bromophenyl	198	3.5	35	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₄ Br	13.54 (13.75)
4d	4-Methoxyphenyl	165	3.0	30	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅	15.19 (15.64)
4e	4-Methylphenyl	187	3.0	35	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₄	16.12 (16.37)
4f	4-Hydroxyphenyl	173	3.5	30	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₅	15.86 (16.27)
4g	3-Hydroxyphenyl	183	3.5	30	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₅	15.86 (15.27)
4h	3-Nitrophenyl	194	4.0	25	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ O ₆	18.47 (18.76)
4i	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	179	4.0	25	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	13.65 (14.10)
4j	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	187	4.0	25	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	13.85 (14.10)

* Recrystallisation solvent : ethanol - acetone.

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF PHENYLHYDRAZONES (6)

Compd.	Ar	M.p.* °C	Reaction time, h	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
6a	Phenyl	289	10	70	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅	12.07 (12.44)
6b	2-Chlorophenyl	242	10	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₅ Cl	11.37 (11.57)
6c	2-Bromophenyl	219	10	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₅ Br	10.19 (10.58)
6d	4-Methoxyphenyl	208	10	65	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	11.49 (11.66)
6e	4-Methylphenyl	210	10	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₅	11.79 (12.06)
6f	4-Hydroxyphenyl	197	10	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₆	11.50 (12.01)
6g	3-Hydroxyphenyl	205	10	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₆	11.83 (12.01)
6h	3-Nitrophenyl	245	10	55	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₇	13.85 (14.14)
6i	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	227	10	50	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	10.29 (10.78)
6j	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	235	10	50	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	10.59 (10.78)

* Recrystallisation solvent : ethanol - acetone.

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